

The Degree of Availability of Professional Teaching Competencies for Physical Education Teachers in Jordan

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ABSTRACT

Given the importance of the teacher's role in the classroom ; Educational institutions have been keen to rehabilitate and train him to carry out the tasks entrusted to him, whether before service through programs and courses offered in institutes and universities, or during service through training courses with the aim of developing many of his skills so that he possesses a set of educational competencies that he needs to transfer educational experiences Therefore, this study came, which aimed to identify the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view and its relationship to some variables such as gender, academic qualification and years of experience, where the descriptive approach was used in addition to The questionnaire consisting of (40) paragraphs and distributed into four areas as a tool for the study. The study sample consisted of (784) male and female teachers in the second semester of the year (2021/2022) ; The study concluded that the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies was moderately in all fields of study, in addition to the absence of statistically significant differences that are attributed to the variables of gender and educational qualification, and the presence of statistically significant differences due to the variable years of experience and in favor of teachers with experience of more than 10 years.

Keywords : *vocational training; professional qualification*

INTRODUCTION

The recommendations of the educational conferences in general are hardly devoid of a focus on the importance of preparing the teacher and rehabilitating him with sufficient skills that enable him to perform his teaching role efficiently, in the belief and proof that the efficient teacher is the key to success and the cornerstone of any educational system, and no matter how many studies and theses about what the role of the teacher is except It remains the decisive factor in preparing and directing students to the maximum of their preparations and abilities (Al-Khasawneh, 2013; Youssef et al., 2018).

The studies that dealt with the

criteria that determine the competence of the teacher or the quality of the program that he completed vary, but most contemporary trends depend on the competency system in preparing, rehabilitating and evaluating teachers, and this trend emerged from the beginning in the United States of America in the seventies of the last century and spread widely in colleges Education around the world and continued to the present time, and the report of the International Committee for Education, Culture and Science of UNESCO reinforces the importance of the system of teaching competencies in preparing teachers and stresses the need to continuously improve their teaching

competencies, starting from teacher preparation programs in colleges of education to continuing teacher training programs to serve the quality of Education and achieve the aspirations of students in the twenty-first century (Khazali, Momni, 2007).

The trends of thinkers and educators about the concept of professional teaching competence vary, but there is almost agreement that it is the ability of the teacher and enables him, behaviorally and skillfully, to conduct the educational process efficiently and help students to develop comprehensive and integrated (Kim, 2000).

Al Shugairat (2009) believes that professional teaching competencies are nothing but an elaborate system that combines teacher behaviors, behaviors, attitudes, skills and knowledge. There is also a difference between teacher preparation colleges about determining what competencies teachers must possess, and after reviewing teacher preparation programs in universities and reviewing theoretical literature, The two researchers pointed out that the basic professional competencies that the teacher must possess are planning, implementation, teaching methods and evaluation, and also the need for training student teachers and continuing training of continuing teachers to link these competencies to ensure the achievement of the desired quality in the teacher.

His Excellency and Ibrahim (2001) indicate that there are four methods dealt with by the theoretical heritage and studies to derive or determine the professional teaching competencies for teachers. The first is to follow up and study the case of distinguished teachers to determine aspects of their teaching effectiveness and determine the competencies as a consequence. The

second method focuses on studying the opinions of the field. The educator is an expert in preparing teachers about the importance and nature of the competencies needed for teachers, while the third method derives the teaching competencies from carrying out scientific studies and research papers that deal with the factors affecting the educational process and their repercussions on the teacher preparation process, and the fourth method is related to the analysis of the educational system using the systems analysis method to identify The importance and role of parts in the overall process.

The physical education teacher shares with the teachers of the rest of the subjects the need to possess these competencies. Rather, they are more likely to achieve the goals or competencies expected to be achieved by students, due to the nature of the physical education lesson that students like and their motivation towards it, as well as the role of the physical education teacher, which often exceeds the educational content Or the skill to self-esteem, direct and motivate students, in addition to the impact of internal and external sports activities on them (Al-Zuhairi, 2006; Youssef et al., 2018).

The study problem

1) The teacher is the organizer and facilitator of the process of student education, as students are affected by any educational and creative program through the teacher, so it can be said that the effectiveness of educational institutions depends directly on the adequacy of their employees, so raising the efficiency of the teacher is one of the goals of the educational institution. The basic requirements for teachers, for the sake of the success of the educational

process, so many studies in the educational and sports field have focused on studying the educational competencies of teachers, 2) Many physical education experts believe that those in charge of teaching physical education in schools must possess the professional teaching competencies necessary to teach various sports skills. Job licensing certificate by graduating from specialized colleges. There is no doubt that teachers' possession of professional teaching competencies will develop their capabilities, enrich their experiences, and help them achieve educational goals, within a framework that facilitates meeting their needs. Therefore, disclosing the extent of their availability is critical, because it will help identify points Their weakness and strength, and then address them (Youssef et al., 2018), 3) Through the researchers' contact with the educational community, they noticed a weakness in the performance of physical education teachers, which urged them to this study to determine the professional teaching competencies that physical education teachers must have in Jordan, to help the teacher master the teaching of physical education, because this subject has A significant impact on the development of the student's personality, a comprehensive and balanced development in all different aspects of life, which helps in raising the level of efficiency in his performance, and whose impact on the educational process as a whole is evident.

Based on the foregoing, this study seeks to answer the following questions

1) What is the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan

from their point of view? 2) Are there statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view, which are attributed to the gender variable? 3) Are there statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view that are attributed to the educational qualification variable? 4) Are there statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view, which are attributed to the variable number of years of experience?

Objectives of the study

The study aims to

1) Identifying the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view, 2) Find out if there are statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view, which are attributed to the study variables, which are Gender, educational qualification and number of years of experience?

The importance of studying

In addition to the fact that this study is a continuation of the related studies that deal with the professional teaching competencies of physical education teachers in Jordan, it will also help the physical education teachers in question to identify the reality of their professional teaching competencies,

which may help them improve and develop them, and on the other hand it will give those in charge of the educational process In the faculties of physical education, the Jordanian Ministry of Education is an indicator of the quality of the physical education program and the effectiveness of teaching for teachers.

The limits of the study

This study was limited to identifying the professional teaching competencies of physical education teachers in Jordan for the following professional teaching competencies: (planning, implementation, teaching methods and evaluation) in the schools of the Jordanian Ministry of Education. The study was implemented in the academic year (2012/2022).

Previous studies

A group of studies related to the issue of professional teaching competencies for teachers was referred to, which were summarized as follows ; 1) The study (Youssef et al., 2018) came to identify the teaching competencies of physical education teachers in special education schools in the State of Kuwait, where the descriptive approach and the questionnaire tool that were applied to (116) teachers were used. Only one and a weak degree on the rest of the fields, in addition to the lack of interaction between the variables of the study and the teaching competencies, 2) Conducted (Mohamed and Imbabi,(2004 study aimed at identifying the extent to which physical education teachers mastered the teaching competencies in the second cycle of basic education.” The research sample consisted of 37 technical mentors and 250 physical education teachers. Contrary to the adequacy of teaching

methods and assessment, where they are appended to the list of competencies arrangement, 3) Abdul Haq (2004) also conducted a study aimed at identifying the “basic competencies of school sports teachers in the first basic stage in Nablus, where the sample consisted of 60 male and female teachers who showed a very great ability in the adequacy of choosing educational goals and in the adequacy of choosing activities in general, as he showed Teachers have a very great ability in the adequacy of assessment, as the results show their skill in evaluating students' performance in their motor and skill tests and the use of formative assessment, 4) Hassan, (2004) study, which aimed to "know the teaching competencies of physical education teachers in the Kingdom of Bahrain" indicated that the total competencies that physical education teachers enjoy a large degree of possession of competencies in general. He also concluded in his study that the absence of statistically significant differences It can be attributed to the gender variable, while the study showed that there were statistically significant differences due to the educational stage variable in favor of the secondary stage and to the experience variable in favor of teachers with less than ten years of experience, 5) And (Abdul-Baqi et al., 2011, in their study, which aimed to identify the teaching competencies of physical education teachers in the intermediate stage in the provinces of the Middle Euphrates in Iraq, which was applied to 120 teachers, concluded that the degree of teachers' possession of educational competencies was medium, where the adequacy of goals came In the first place to a large extent, followed by the competencies of planning,

Table 1
Distribution of Individuals According to Study Variables

Percentage	the Number	Categories	Variable
61%	476	Male	Sex
39%	308	Feminine	
100%	784	Total	
76%	596	Bachelor of	Qualification
24%	188	Postgraduate	
100%	784	Total	
32%	248	1-5 years	Teaching Experience
39%	304	5-10 years	
29%	232	more than 10 years	
100%	784	Total	

implementation, evaluation and teaching methods, and all of them came to a medium degree, 6) Al-Rawahi and Al-Hanai (2013) conducted a study aimed at identifying the “teaching competencies of physical education teachers in the Sultanate of Oman” as well as identifying whether there were any statistical differences that could be attributed to the variables of gender, experience and educational area. The sample included 310 teachers and reached The researchers indicated that teachers had adequate planning with a degree that ranged between medium and high, while the adequacy of implementation was generally high, while the results showed a significant decrease in the degree of teaching adequacy of evaluation. , while the study showed that there were statistically significant differences due to the variable of the educational region in favor of teachers with longer experience in all competencies.

Commenting on previous studies

Previous studies reviewed the professional teaching competencies of

physical education teachers in general, and dealt in parts of them with their reality or degree of possession and development, and were also exposed to the study of multiple variables such as gender, teaching experience, stage and educational area; The studies showed a discrepancy in the degree of possession of professional teaching competencies and their relationship to the variables, and the researchers benefited from the theoretical literature of these studies and the tools used in them, but there is a very clear shortcoming in recent studies in this field, which may give this study a new dimension and an additional advantage that enriches the theoretical literature in the study of competencies Professional teaching for physical education teachers in Jordan.

RESEARCH METHODS

Field study procedures

Study approach

The researchers used the comparative descriptive approach for its suitability to the nature of the study, as it deals with identifying problems, explaining conditions and phenomena,

Table 2
The Internal Consistency of the Scale Dimensions

Internal Consistency Coefficient	the Field
0,59-0,64	Planning
0,67-0,71	Execution
0,37-0,63	Calendar
0,64-0,58	Teaching Methods

and clarifying the existing relationships and their implications (Abu Hatab and Sadiq, 2010).

Study community

The study population consisted of all physical education teachers working in the schools of the Jordanian Ministry of Education during the academic year (2021/2022), and their number was (4987), according to the statistics of the Jordanian Ministry of Education.

The study sample

An electronic questionnaire prepared by the researchers was distributed randomly to physical education teachers through various electronic means of communication such as WhatsApp and Facebook, where (784) male and female teachers responded to the questionnaire; Table No. (1) shows the distribution of study members according to its variables :

Study tool

The study tool was built by reviewing relevant literature and research studies. In its initial form, the scale included (58) items distributed over the four fields of study; Each paragraph was given a weight listed according to the five-point Likert scale, strongly agree (5 degrees), agree to some extent (four degrees), neutral (three degrees), disagree (two degrees), strongly disagree (one degree) in order to estimate the degree of Availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan.

Authenticity of the tool

The validity of the study tool was confirmed by following the following methods : 1) The validity of the arbitrators (veracity of the content) : to ensure the validity of the study tool, the questionnaire was presented in its initial form to a group of specialized arbitrators from university professors, professional

Table 3
Cronbach's Alpha Invariance for Scale Fields

Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient	the Hub
0,68	Planning
0,63	Execution
0,71	Calendar
0,59	Teaching Methods

Table 4
Distribution Of Scale Dimensions Scores Over Study Periods

The Extent to Which Teachers Apply the Dimension			the Field
High	Average	Low	
29,5 – 40,0	18,7 – 29,4	8,0 – 18,6	Planning
33,0 – 45,0	22,0 – 32,9	9,0 – 21,9	Execution
25,7 – 35,0	16,3 – 25,6	7,0 – 16,2	Calendar
33,0 – 45,0	22,0 – 32,9	9,0 – 21,9	Teaching Methods

education supervisors and vocational education teachers, numbering (12) arbitrators, in order to express their opinion on the appropriateness of the questionnaire's paragraphs for what is to be measured, in addition to making any corrections they deem appropriate. Linguistically, deleting and adding some paragraphs; Where the arbitrators made their observations of the process of deleting some paragraphs and merging others; The questionnaire, in its final form, consisted of (40) items distributed equally among the fields of study.

2) Statistical validity : the validity of the scale was calculated statistically by means of internal consistency validity, which showed high consistency between the paragraphs of each domain and between the domains as a whole, which indicates its sincerity in measuring what was set for it. The following table No. (2) illustrates this :

Tool stability

The stability of the study tool was verified by calculating Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the domains of the scale, from which it was clear that the questionnaire in all its fields had a high degree of stability that makes the researchers assured of the accuracy of the results that will be collected through them. The following table No. (3)

illustrates this :

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results related to the first study question, which states :

What is the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view? To answer this question, the confidence interval test was applied. This test is based on dividing the range of degrees of the scale applied in the study into several small periods of equal length ranging from 3-5 periods, so that these periods are graded in their severity or application of the measured phenomenon, then The test drops the confidence interval for the average of the study population that was obtained after analyzing the data of that scale over those periods, through which the extent to which the study sample can apply this phenomenon can be determined.

Since the study contains four areas of professional teaching competencies, the researchers divided the degree range of each dimension into three periods. The following table No. (4) shows the distribution of those periods on the fields :

As for estimating the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan, the following table

Table 5
Arithmetic Averages, Standard Deviations, and Confidence Intervals for Areas of Professional Teaching Competencies

Confidence Period		Indication	degrees of Freedom	t value	Standard Deviation	SMA	the Field
the Highest Rate	Minimum						
20,3	19,8	0,001	109	23,4	6,3	32,4	planning
25,0	23,2	0,001	109	22,7	5,4	29,7	Execution
18,8	17,2	0,001	109	30,4	4,3	24,3	Calendar
26,9	24,8	0,001	109	32,1	3,6	22,3	Teaching Methods

No. (5) shows those results :

It is clear by reviewing the results contained in Table (5) that physical education teachers in Jordan have professional teaching competencies at a medium degree, as the confidence period for the planning field ranged between (19,8-20,3), for the implementation field, between (23,2-25,0) and for the evaluation field between (17,2- 18,8) and the field of teaching methods ranged between (24,8-26,9) and this indicates that teachers still need to develop their cognitive abilities and expertise in a better way; Here, we must recall the Corona pandemic, which began in 2019 and is still continuing until the moment, which contributed to the decline in the level of professional competencies among teachers, due to the distance

education period, which affected the level of teaching performance of teachers.

The focus of the faculties of physical education in particular and the faculties of education and teacher preparation in general on the theoretical and cognitive aspects and the lack of focus on the practical aspects contributes to the existence of gaps in the level of professional competencies for teachers.

In addition to what was previously mentioned, the failure of physical education colleges to familiarize students with professional competencies, in addition to the failure of the Jordanian Ministry of Education to continuously train and qualify teachers according to the competency system for supervision and then evaluate their performance to

Table 6
The Results Of The "t" Test for the Significance of the Differences in the Degree of Availability of Professional Teaching Competencies for Physical Education Teachers, Which Are Attributed to the "Sex" Variable (Males, Females)

Indication	t	Female		Male		Fields	Number
		Standard Deviation	SMA	Standard Deviation	SMA		
0,14	1,66	0,57	3,22	0,58	3,33	Planning	1
0,25	1,52	0,63	3,27	0,57	3,25	Execution	2
0,13	1,33	0,60	3,19	0,61	3,36	Calendar	3
0,27	1,42	0,55	3,12	0,59	3,21	Teaching Methods	4
0,11	1,32	0,61	3,14	0,60	3,21	Total Marks	

Table 7
The Results of the "t" Test for the Significance of the Differences in the Degree of Availability of Professional Teaching Competencies for Physical Education Teachers, Which are Attributed to the "Scientific Qualification" Variable (Bachelor, Postgraduate)

Indication	t	Postgraduate		Bachelor of		Fields	Number
		Standard Deviation	SMA	Standard Deviation	SMA		
0,15	1,25	0,62	3,40	0,66	3,42	Planning	1
0,33	1,64	0,52	3,38	0,64	3,36	Execution	2
0,17	1,37	0,50	3,37	0,59	3,35	Calendar	3
0,09	1,94	0,71	3,29	0,59	3,30	Teaching Methods	4
0,19	1,09	0,68	3,30	0,61	3,28	Total Marks	

determine their level, in a way that develops the educational process and achieves its goals.

The results of the current study agreed with the results of the study (Hassan, 2004), (Mohammed and Imbabi, 2004), (Abdul-Baqi et al., 2011), (Al-Rawahi and Al-Hinai, 2013).

The second question which states: Are there any statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view that are attributed to the gender variable?

To answer the question, a test was used (T-test) to indicate the differences

between groups, and the following table No. (6) shows this :

Table Number (6) indicates that there are no statistically significant differences on the fields of study as a whole and the total degree, which are attributed to the gender variable; This result may be attributed to the level of similarity between the conditions facing teachers, whether they are males or females.

The third question, which states : are there statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view that

Table 8
Arithmetic Averages of Professional Teaching Competencies for Physical Education Teachers Due to the Variable Number of Years of Experience

More Than 10 Years	5-10 Years	1-5 Years	Fields	Number
3,39	3,32	3,35	Planning	1
3,32	3,31	3,30	Execution	2
3,28	3,25	3,28	Calendar	3
3,22	3,21	2,24	Teaching Methods	4
3,21	3,19	3,24	Total Marks	

Table 9
The Results of the One-Way Variance Analysis of the Significance of the Differences in the Degree of Professional Teaching Competencies for Physical Education Teachers, Which are Attributed to the Variable (Number Of Years Of Experience)

Indication*	q Calculated	Mean Deviation	Degrees of Freedom	Sum of Square Deviations	Contrast Source	Fields	Number
0,88	0,154	0,45 0,65	3 88 90	0,089 63,02 63,11	between groups within groups groups total	Planning	1
0,56	0,257	0,484 0,493	3 88 90	0,96 47,35 48,32	between groups within groups groups total	Execution	2
0,95	0,225	0,222 0,635	3 88 90	0,444 61,003 61,447	between groups within groups groups total	Calendar	3
0,34	0,137	0,082 0,322	3 88 90	0,165 30,952 31,117	between groups within groups groups total	Teaching Methods	4
112	0,634	0,71 0,384	3 88 90	0,142 36,907 37,049	between groups within groups groups total	Total	

are attributed to the educational qualification variable (bachelor, postgraduate)?

To answer the question, a test was used. T-test) to indicate the differences between groups and the following table No. (7) shows this :

Table Number (7) indicates that there are no statistically significant differences on the fields of study as a whole and the total degree, which are attributed to the educational qualification variable; This result may be attributed to the level of similarity between the conditions facing physical education

teachers, whether they hold a bachelor's degree or graduate studies, because the Ministry of Education provides its services to teachers regardless of the teacher's degree.

The fourth question, which states : are there statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan from their point of view, which are attributed to the variable number of years of experience (1-5 years, 5-10 years, more than 10 years)?

To answer this question, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was used. One Way ANOVA) and the results of Table (8) show the arithmetic means, while the results of Table (9) show the results of the one-way analysis of variance.

Table Number (9) indicates that there are statistically significant differences in all fields and in the total degree according to the variable number of years of experience and in favor of more than 10 years. This result is natural, since the ancient teachers were exposed to many skills and successively more than the other teachers; Also, the teaching process is a cumulative process. The more years of service, the higher the teacher's teaching competencies This result agrees with the results of the study of (Al-Khasawneh, 2013), (Khazali and Al-Momani, 2007) and (Abdul-Baqi et al., 2011) and contradicts the results of the study (Hassan, 2004).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study aimed to identify the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers in Jordan. The results also indicated that there were no statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers, which are attributed to the variables of gender and the teacher's academic qualification. The results showed that there were statistically significant differences in the degree of availability of professional teaching competencies for physical education teachers, which were attributed to the variable years of experience for the teacher, which was in favor of those with more than 10 years

of experience. The results show, in general, a clear shortcoming and weakness of teachers in their professional teaching competencies, which calls for those in charge of the educational process in the Jordanian Ministry of Education to tighten teacher appointment policies and review the reasons why current teachers have weak teaching competencies that threaten the achievement of the desired education goals.

In light of the results of the study, the researchers recommend the following : 1) Developing a physical education teaching program in physical education faculties, 2) Encouraging physical education teachers to complete their studies to enable them to teach effectively and cover existing deficiencies, 3) Preparing the Ministry of Education for a mandatory training plan in professional teaching competencies, the passing of which is linked to the promotion and financial and professional promotion of teachers and 4) Conducting more research and studies and expanding the sample circle to include educational supervisors, school administrations and parents.

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